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Name: Anthony Oluwatoyin Afuye-Cyrus

Student ID: 20026532

Supervisor's name: Peter Franklin

Abstract

Many people with deafness or hearing challenges have been able to communicate with the hearing world today using the advantages the advancement in technology has provided for the world globe. However, the application of Computer Vision with Deep Learning for Real-time Sign Language Recognition has tremendously bridged the gap between signers and non-signers, eliminating interference of human interpreters. Moreover, using the MediaPipe framework as one of the most broadly shared and reusable libraries when it concerns media processing is also adopted within the Computer Vision with Deep Learning technique to customize the Machine Learning solution for the real-time sign language recognition in the project.

The focus of this project work is to develop a computer vision application that helps in the automatic conversion of hand gestures into texts and speech in British Sign Language without the use of a human interpreter as well as enhancing effective communication between signers and non-signer. The model put in place in the course of the project work extracts both spatial and temporal features from video sequences. There is an in-built webcam of a computer system used to capture video sequences using OpenCv that track the gestures. The application is also trained to recognize signs given out effective outputs with the smallest delay within an immediate time frame. The dataset used is the self-generated dataset modeled for British Sign Language usage.

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MSc Final Project Declaration

This report is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the degree of Master of Science in Artificial Intelligence and Robotics at the University of Hertfordshire (UH).

It is my own work except where indicated in the report.

I did not use human participants in my MSc Project.

I hereby give permission for the report to be made available on the university website provided the source is acknowledged.

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CHAPTER 1

1.0 Introduction

The chapter introduction brings up the study overview, with a description of the study work, and project goal as well as the report of the study

1.1 Overview of the study

Numerous people from all over the world have adapted sign language communication to interrelate with the rest of the world. It will be interesting to know about the thrilling technological development that helps people with hearing challenges or deafness to communicate with the hearing world. This is made possible with the help of machine translation systems for sign language. The systems automatically convert signs into text or spoken dialogue, and then back to sign language without the interference of a human interpreter (*Everything You Need to Know About Machine Translation for Sign Language*, no date)

With the recent advancement in technology, it is easy to translate any telecast that involves sign language, using devices that respond to sign language commands (*Sign Language Recognition using Densenet-Deep Learning Projects*, no date).

However, It has been estimated by the World Health Organization's (WHO) first World Report on Hearing that by 2050 close to 2.5 billion people worldwide will be living with some degree of hearing loss (*WHO: 1 in 4 people projected to have hearing problems by 2050*, no date). These speech-impaired people can get their thoughts across to the other person using visual means and hand gestures, known as Sign Language Communication (Nihalaani, 2021). Currently, we have several existing sign languages around the globe whose successes are based on "Human Interpreter (HI)". In having a seamless Sign Language Operation, there is a need to look into the challenge of HI using an efficient Machine Learning technique.

In the course of this study, my emphasis is based on British Sign Language (BSL) using computer vision and deep learning. Moreover, considering Britain, BSL is a language that is independent and not related to spoken English. BSL is one of the common forms of Sign Language with self-contained grammatical structure and syntax, and it is the language that is mainly used and recognized by around 145,000 people within the United Kingdom (UK) 2011(*Language - Office for National Statistics*, no date). IBM, best-described computer vision as a field of artificial intelligence (AI) that enables computers and systems to derive meaningful information from digital images, videos, and other visual inputs(Jiao *et al.*, 2019). Research has it as a field of computer science that focuses on enabling computers to identify and understand objects and people in images and videos(Oktem *et al.*, 2021).

1.2 Study Definition and History

1.2.1 Brief Definition

Computer Vision (CV) (*Computer vision - Wikipedia*, no date) (Jiao *et al.*, 2019) can be defined or termed as an interdisciplinary field of study that combines different areas of study like engineering and computer science (Artificial Intelligence) whereby computer system could be made to achieve a great level of understanding from videos sequences or other visual inputs and digital images, automating the same work using computer visual system (Hasan and Kashevnik, 2021). It focused on the automatic extraction, exploration, and understanding of meaningful information from either a single or sequence of images. There are various forms the image data can take like views from multiple cameras, video sequences, and multi-dimensional data from medical scanners (Kakaletsis *et al.*, 2021).

1.2.2 Brief History

The ground breakthrough of Computer Vision (CV) became materialized in 2012 when AlexNet won ImageNet. In that same 2012, Sir Geoffrey Hinton and his noble students won the 2012 ImageNet competition. AlexNet happened to be the first architecture after LeNet that eventually brought a great revolution into the industry of Deep Learning where the Deep Learning technique was adopted. Part of the achievements was to attain a Top-5 error of 15.3% in the ImageNet Challenge which was by then 10.8% lower than the runner-up. This famous AlexNet that won the 2012 ImageNet LSVRC-2012 competition by a far large margin (15.3% vs 26.6% (second place) error rate) adopted Relu in place of Tanh to complement non-linearity, also made use of dropout in the place of regularization to resolve the issue of overfitting and also adopted overlapping pooling to reduce the network size (*AlexNet in depth. AlexNet was designed by Sir Geoffrey... | by Mustafa | Medium*, no date) but before then CV started in the late 1960s at the various universities pioneering Artificial Intelligence (AI). The objective back then was to mimic the Human Visual System (HVS), as a means of endowing robots with intelligent behavior. The development continued, and in 1966, it was agreed that it could be made a temporary project whereby a camera could be attached to a computer and be made to describe what it saw (Vandoni, 1996).

However, the Progressive development experienced in the 1970s provided early grounds for many of the computer vision algorithms that is existing today. In the 1990s we began to see activeness in some of the previous research topics for instance research in Projective 3-D Reconstructions which brought a better understanding of Cameral Calibration (CC) (Soltani *et al.*, 2017). Several innovations and ideas emerged in Bundle Adjustment theory from the Photogrammetry field of study that led to the methods for sparse 3-D Reconstructions of scenes from multiple images, so also the extraction of three-dimensional structure from images which distinguished computer vision from the prevailing field of Digital Image Processing (DIP) also emerged (Oktem *et al.*, 2021). Recently we have also seen the emergency of feature-based methods used in combination with machine learning techniques and complex optimization frameworks development, for the accuracy of Deep Learning techniques algorithms

(Balasundaram *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, several tasks varying from classification, segmentation, and optical flow have exceeded previous methods as a result of the accuracy of deep learning algorithms in various standard computer vision data sets (Maity, 2016)

1.3.0 Deep Learning Definition and History

1.3.1 Deep Learning Definition

Deep Learning is a wider family of Machine Learning algorithms that progressively makes use of multiple layers to extract higher-level features of raw input. An instance of this can be seen in Image Processing, where the higher layers may detect the conceptions that are related to a human-like digit, letters, or face while lower layers may detect edges (Feng *et al.*, 2019).

Machine Learning is a field of study that focuses on building and understanding methods that develop performance on various sets of tasks by data leveraging (Smith and Leymarie, 2017).

1.3.2 Deep Learning History

Various sources have referred to Frank Rosenblatt an American notable psychologist in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) as the one that developed and explored several basic ingredients of the Deep Learning systems of today (*Deep learning - Wikipedia*, no date) (Tappert, 2019) This was as a result of the publication made at Cornell University in 1962 by Cornell Aeronautical Laboratory, Inc., in his book “Principles of Neurodynamics: Perceptrons and the Theory of Brain Mechanisms”(*Cornell University Technical Reports (including Cornell Aeronautical Lab) - Technical reports (NASA, DOE, etc.) - LibGuides at Cornell University*, no date)

However, Deep learning history could be traced back to 1943; this was the era of Walter Pitts and Warren McCulloch when a computer model based on the Neural Networks of the human brain was created. Back then it was the combination of algorithms and mathematics called Threshold Logic used to mimic the thought process. Ever since then, Deep Learning has evolved progressively (*A Brief History of Deep Learning - DATAVERSITY*, no date).

In 1967, the first Learning Algorithm used for deep, supervised, feedforward, multilayer perceptrons was made published by Lapa and Alexey Ivakhnenko (*The principle of Deep Learning Essay*, no date). In 1971, there was also a paper published by the group method of data handling that described a Deep Network with trained eight layers (Hinton *et al.*, 2012). In 1980 Neocognitron was introduced by Kunihiko Fukushima, and other Deep Learning working architectures, especially those that were built for Computer Vision emerged (Fukushima, 1980).

In 2000 Deep Learning was introduced to Artificial Neural Networks by Igor Aizenberg in Boolean threshold neurons (Aizenberg, 2011), just as it was introduced in 1986 to Machine Learning Community by Rina Dechter. In the early 2000s Deep Learning become impactful in industry and with Convolutional Neural networks (CNNs) processing nearly all the checks written then which was estimated between 10% to 20% according to Yann LeCun (LeCun *et al.*,

1998) and in 2010 the industrial applications of deep learning to large-scale speech recognition emerged. Currently, the rapid development seen in the Artificial Intelligence class is dependent on Deep Learning where Semantics technology is being used with Deep Learning to bring Artificial Intelligence to the next level to make it sounds natural in conversations like humans, though Deep learning is still developing and require creative ideas. It was suggested in a report from Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) that by 2025, 86% of financial services will increase their Artificial Intelligence investment. Recently, new business models are being influenced by Deep learning and Artificial Intelligence, creating new corporate cultures, automating trading, reducing risk, detecting fraud, and providing AI chatbot advice to investors (*A Brief History of Deep Learning - DATAVERSITY*, no date) etc.

1.5 Study Aims and Objectives

1.5.1 Aims

My aim and focus as regards this project work is to intensively strive in achieving the creation of a very fast real-time dataset that would model British Sign Language as well as its respective real-time recognition into written words.

1.5.2 Objectives

The objectives of this study are as follows:

- To study and acquire good knowledge in Deep Learning Algorithms.
- To gain a good knowledge of Sign Language Communications.
- To implement the knowledge of Deep Learning in Sign Language Annotations.
- To make the systems applicable for the implementations of Deep Learning Algorithms.

1.6 Research Questions

The questions that arise while studying this research work are as follows:

- How does the knowledge of Deep Learning Algorithms apply to BSL?
- How is the knowledge of Computer Vision with Deep learning important for BSL in this study?
- How can the BSL systems be made impactful with the implementation of Deep Learning Algorithms?

1.7 Legal, Ethical, and Professional Issues

My Reflection on Legal, Ethical and Professional Issues as regards Sign Language Recognition using Computer Vision with Deep Learning. It is important to put into consideration the right to privacy of others in line with the Human Rights Code of Conduct, which I believe will help to take the necessary steps against unauthorized collection and disclosure of human personal information to the public (*The Human Rights Act / Equality and Human Rights Commission*, no date). The view of the ACM Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct is also aligned with in doing the project work, more importantly, as it applies to give an all-inclusive and in-depth

evaluation of computer systems as well as their respective impacts which never exempt the analysis of various possible risks (*ACM Code of Ethics and Professional Conduct*, no date).

However, based on what the professional computing body stand on, due consideration and proper care is put in place in the course of this work to avoid discrimination and bias on the premises of gender, religion, harassment, race, and other code of conduct(*BCS, The Chartered Institute for IT / BCS*, no date).

Furthermore, my findings, reports, and results are grounded in consideration and guided by the Legal, Ethical, and Professional Code of Conduct.

Moreover, the consideration of the conscience of the profession is strictly addressed in the course of this project work. The data used as regards Sign Language Recognition using Computer Vision with Deep Learning are the self-generated type of data with the pictures of myself in the project which complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) policy that has put in place the guiding principle to follow in processing and collection of personal information (*General Data Protection Regulation policy - GOV.UK*, no date).

1.8 Chapter Outline

Chapter 1 The chapter entails a brief overview of my studies as well as the study aims and objectives.

Chapter 2 The chapter also reviews the previous related works, and existing and future works with their various impediments.

Chapter 3 The chapter describes and also shows case my way forward to the identified impediments.

Chapter 4 the section will record and do the analyses of the results from the methodology.

Chapter 5 the section will evaluate and gives the result summary report of my studies and also expounds on the expected future development in this field of study.

CHAPTER 2

2.0 Literature Evaluation

In the course of this review, I consider relevant research works which entail previous works, existing as well as what could be the future development that will emerge based on the influence of Computer Vision with Deep Learning in creating and implementing new communication models to ease the concerns at hand. Moreover, as the influence of Computer Vision with Deep Learning continue to advance the course of Sign Language leads to an important question: How is the knowledge of Computer Vision with Deep learning important and be implemented for BSL in this study? Answering such an important question is essential as various previous, existing and future development works have indicated that using these high technological features (Computer Vision with Deep Learning) has further shown us how thriving technology has transformed Sign Language to bring convenience and pleasing interaction to the deaf in the hearing world.

On the bases of British Sign Language using Computer vision with Deep learning, research work papers are reviewed such as (Bantupalli, 2018) (Kothadiya *et al.*, 2022), (Al-qurishi, Khalid and Souissi, 2021), (Lozanova, 2018), (Bandyopadhyay, College and Bengal, 2020), (Sabeenian, Sai Bharathwaj and Mohamed Aadhil, 2020), etc. It is during my review I discovered the need to address the challenge of HI and which in the course of my studies be able to look into it using computer vision a field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) that helps system applications see and understand digital images and videos (*Computer Vision Definition / DeepAI*, no date) with deep learning which is also a kind of machine learning and artificial intelligence that simulate how people acquire specific knowledge (*Deep Learning - Practice Test Geeks*, no date).

In previous years, the development of sign language recognition, generation as well as translational systems always requires expertise in the field of computer vision, graphics, and natural language processing. There should be sufficient expertise also in linguistics and sufficient knowledge about deaf culture. The researchers identified some of the barriers to sign language convolution like sign language usually creating some cultural minorities and many people are considering or viewing deafness as not a disability but as a cultural identity. The work of linguistics had developed some huge respect for sign languages and they also established them as natural languages (Bragg *et al.*, 2019).

Bantupalli and Xie (2018) made elaborate progress using Deep Learning and Computer Vision based techniques in the field of motion and gesture recognition. In their research works, they created a vision-based application that helps the translation of sign language to a readable text. This development aids the challenge of communication between sign language speakers and non-sign language speakers. The objective of the projected model, by Bantupalli and Xie, was to carry out the extraction of Features of both Spatial and Temporal from video sequences. However, an Inception, a known Convolutional Neural Network was used to recognize the extracted Spatial Features while Recurrent Neural Network was also used to train on the

extracted Temporal Features with American Sign Language Dataset created. Despite the promising progress made so far, the model is still faced with the challenge of skin tones and facial features. The model accuracy dropped when being subjected to different skin tones testing as well as with varying signer face inclusion hence the model ended up training wrong features from the videos even with variation in clothing.

Gomaa, Gla, and Elrayes, (2021) in the provision of their applied research work in which an Egyptian sign language recognition system (video-based) was developed to bridge the existing communication gap among the deaf people in Egypt's local community area. Two different neural network architectures, namely Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for extraction of spatial features, and Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) for extraction of both spatial and temporary features of a computer vision system were presented. The neural network architectures set up respectively attained an accuracy of 90% and 72%. The main challenge as regards Egyptian Sign Language is the variation from one local community of deaf people to the other.

Chavan, Yu, and Saniie (2021) the authors' approach was based on using deep learning to identify American Sign Language to capture the image as input. The application system could predict ten digits ranging from 0 to 9 by the signer. In the experiment, image processing was utilized for the conversion of RGB data to grayscale images that efficiently helped in size reduction in achieving storage requirements and Convolutional Neural Network training time. The motive of the experiment is to use the combination of Image Processing and Deep Learning Architecture that has lesser complexity for the deployment of embedded single-board computers or mobile applications. Part of the things done in the experiment was the database training from the scratch using smaller networks such as AlexNet and Lenet-5 as well as Deeper networks like Vgg16 and MobileNet v2. In the course of the experiment, it was discovered that the transfer learning approach with ImageNet weights was not appropriate in terms of performance for American Sign Language and part of the challenges was the unsatisfying result of Deeper as well as smaller networks so also the dataset size.

Krishnan and Balasubramanian, (2019) research work on the use of Convolutional tools was adopted for sign language translation which encompasses the application of linear classifiers like Support Vector Machine and KNN to carry out the classification of hand gesture images. However, for automation of both features extraction and selection procedure a Deep Neural Network based machine translation was used. Based on the experiment carried out the images of English Sign Language were identified using the approach of Deep Learning. The architectural design entails a custom Deep Neural Network with three convolution layers and three Max-Pooling layers. The system was designed to validate the detection of hand gesture images in the research paper. Moreover, the expected development will be achieved in English Sign Language machine translation when the experiment is done with more Convolution blocks and different optimizer functions.

Lakhotiya, Pandita, and Shankarmani, (2021) research done by authors was based on real-time recognition of sign language using image classification. Classification of images using a Convolution Neural network is a vital component of Computer Vision. The objective of the work is to project a real-time sign language application system that is based on American Sign Language that will aid effective communication among the deaf in a hearing world by translating sign language gestures into text and speech in the English Language. A computer system with a

built-in webcam using OpenCV was the type of video-capturing system that was used to track hand gestures. However, Convolutional Neural Networks, a known potent deep learning tool was adopted in training the system to recognize signs. The method used helped in giving effective output with less significant or rather minimum delay in real-time. Moreover, the algorithm projected in the research work translated the sign language in real-time with few challenges. Among the few challenges is the issue of a plain background, the user must have a plain background when giving the input otherwise the pre-processing stage will lead to abnormalities. More works still need to be done in this area using the same algorithm with adjustments regardless of the background. Skin with various colors can be used when detecting hand gestures to tackle this challenge. Also, more than one camera can be mounted to capture hand gestures from different angles; these and many more can be explored in future related research works.

2.1 Deep Learning Techniques

Several methodologies have been adopted to look into the challenge of Hand Gesture Recognition (HGR) in videos via different approaches as regards the literature review of the issue (Bantupalli, 2018). HGR is a competitive area of study that requires the usage of sensory hardware for gesture recognition. Though the usage of hardware is costly but less convenient in real life. However, the use of computer vision techniques gives researchers the hope of getting the best recognition accuracy.

Moreover, gesture recognition performance and vision were based on sign language detection which was compared (Sruthi and Lijiya, 2019). Deep Learning techniques have more advantages, such easy to use ability that help in extracting the features from the raw database, and Gesture Recognition Modules (GRM) have also been designed in a way to be able to recognize signs from selfie videos taken on mobile phone (Sruthi and Lijiya, 2019).

2.2 Core Description of Deep Learning

Deep Learning also referred to as Deep Structured Learning can be supervised, semi-supervised or unsupervised originating from the family of machine learning methods that are grounded on a couple of both artificial neural networks and representative learning. There are various architectures of deep learning among them are Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Deep Neural Networks (DNN), Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), Deep Neural Networks (Deep Neural Networks), Deep Belief Networks (DBN) and also Transformers.

Deep Learning application has also been included in various fields of study in which outstanding results has been produced that exceeded human expert performance such as Computer Vision, Natural Language Processing, Speech Recognition, Machine Translation, Bioinformatics, Drug Design, Climate Science, Medical Image Analysis, Board Game Programs, and Material Inspection. Using the word Deep in Deep Learning tells us more about the use of unbounded, multiple layers of the bounded size that enhance the implementation of real-world applications. Deep Learning as a class of Machine Learning Algorithms uses multiple numbers of layers to gradually extract higher-level features from the raw input this we have seen this in some of its applications like Image Processing which the lower layer may detect edges while the higher layers may also recognize the perceptions relevant to human such as skin tone, letters, digits and faces(*Computer vision - Wikipedia*, no date).

2.3 Deep Learning Functionality

Deep learning as a subset of Machine Learning works on the precept of simulating or mimicking the human brain through the grouping of data, bias, and weight. The essence of this is to allow the collaboration of the grouped elements accurately detect, classify and give a description of objects in the data. The Deep Neural Network is made up of multiple numbers of connected layers that help its data and algorithms emulate how humans learn and make adjustments for improvements and accuracy. However, each layer depends on others to enhance its detection or classification progressively. This progressive computation of the Deep Neural Network is referred to as forward propagation. So also backpropagation entails the use of algorithms such as Gradient Descent for calculating errors that comes up at prediction and by adjusting through moving backward the layers in an attempt to train the model, the function of the group elements; weights, and biases. The combination of both backward and forward propagation enhances Neural Network in making prediction and gradually improve accuracy over time (Kothadiya *et al.*, 2022).

In Deep Neural Network some inputs and outputs layers are called visible layers. The input layer of Deep Learning makes provision for data to be processed while the output layer makes room for the last stage of prediction and categorization. Moreover, the algorithm of deep learning is complex and specific based on its datasets(*The principle of Deep Learning Essay*, no date).

2.4 Types of Deep Neural Networks

I would like to discuss the three current popularly used Deep Neural Networks:

1. Recurrent Neural Networks (CNN)
2. Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)
3. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)

2.4.1 Recurrent Neural Network (RNN)

This is one of the families of Artificial Neural Networks that adopts the use of the Sequential Data Feeding technique to resolve the time-series issues that are related to sequential input data. RNN has both current and previous inputs, and because RNN has internal memory it becomes easy to record computation from preceding samples.

2.4.2 Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLPs)

Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) belongs to a feedforward Artificial Neural Network that has sequences of fully connected layers. The machine learning methods of MLP models are made up of various fully connected layers which can be explored to resolve what is necessary for the high computing power of modern deep learning architectures.

2.4.3 Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)

Convolutional Neural Networks also belong to the group of Deep Neural Networks which is mostly used in Computer Vision. However, the AI system in CNN learns the automatic extraction of features from the inputs to complete the specific task. The task to do here could be face authentication, image classification, image semantic segmentation, etc. Moreover, one or

multiple numbers of convolution layers extract the features from the input features through the operation of Convolution.

2.4.4 Deep Learning Rationale

Individuals with hearing disabilities can be found all over the world. Hence, the improvisation of sign language is very predominant in terms of interacting with the hearing world. The evolution of effectual local-level sign language recognition or SLR tools is very important (Al-qurishi, Khalid and Souissi, 2021).

Nowadays, the standard machine learning procedures have been widely changed with bigger architecture that utilizes several layers and passes details in vector format between layers. This is what Deep Learning is all about. It is also known as a deep neural network and they work on strategies that are close to the strategies of Machine Learning. However, Deep Learning complexities are much greater than Machine Learning complexities (Al-qurishi, Khalid and Souissi, 2021). As a result, Deep Learning is more time-consuming as compared to Machine Learning.

2.5 Deep Neural Network Model Functionality

The Recognition of the hand gestures that are based on extracted features is categorized into three groups which are as follows:

- i. High Level Features Based Approaches
- ii. Low Level Features Based Approaches
- iii. 3D Reconstruction-Based Approaches

2.5.1 High Level Features Based Approaches

The implored objective here is to figure out the position of the joint angles and the palm such as joint locations and fingertips of the palm (Chua, Guan and Ho, 2002) (*Y.Li, Hand Gesture Recognition Using Kinect, 2012 - Yahoo Search Results*, no date) (*Hand gesture recognition based on shape parameters | IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore*, no date) (Maisto *et al.*, 2013). The effect collisions on the image are difficult after the extraction of the features (Erol *et al.*, 2007) as well as a sensitive segment that are done on 2D hand images (Ren, Meng and Yuan, 2011) are mostly reoccurring issues. The set of rules and conditions as regards the vectors and joints of the hands define the hand gestures (Cardoso, Delgado and Barata, 2015)

2.5.2 Low-Level Feature-Based Approaches (LLFBA)

The extraction of these features leads to increasing the model's accuracy. The author Zhou, referred to the discovery recognition of the hand shape to be a cluster-based signature that makes

use of a novel distance metric called Finger Earth's Distance ((13) (PDF) *Robust hand gesture recognition based on finger-earth mover's distance with a commodity depth camera*, no date)

The discovery of Author Stanner determines the bounding region of the hand elliptically for implementing hand recognition based on principal axes((13) (PDF) *Robust hand gesture recognition based on finger-earth mover's distance with a commodity depth camera*, no date). Author Yang's research made use of the optical flow of the hand as a low feature ([PDF] *Extraction of 2D Motion Trajectories and Its Application to Hand Gesture Recognition | Semantic Scholar*, no date). When the background is cluttered LLFB becomes less efficient (Ren, Meng and Yuan, 2011)

2.5.3 3D Reconstruction-Based Approaches (3DRBA)

The use of a 3D model of features helps in the complete achievement of hand gesture recognition. The outcome of Bray, Koller-Meier, and Van Gool, 2004 research revealed that background similarity and high contrast are needed for effective segmenting of the hand in color, the well-structured light, tends to bring in the 3D of data depth (Bray, Koller-Meier and Van Gool, 2004). In tracking the various interest points of the superficies of the hand that is difficult in handling even with 3D reconstruction stereo camera is used which contains 3D valuable information

2.6 Hand Gestures Recognition Methods

Following the literature review there are three Hand Gesture Recognition methods that need to be addressed in the course of this review, which is as follows:

- i. Machine Learning Method
- ii. Algorithm Method
- iii. Rule Based Method

2.6.1 Machine Learning Method

This hand gesture is based on the stochastic process and method which is derived from statistical modeling for dynamic gestures like PCA (Lee and Kim, 1999) condensation algorithm (Doucet, Freitas and Gordon, 2001) and particle filtering ([PDF] *Smart particle filtering for 3D hand tracking | Semantic Scholar*, no date)

2.6.2 Algorithm Method

This method is the collection of encoded condition that embraces dynamic gestures; a collection of encoded conditions and restraints manually for defining as gestures in dynamic gestures, in this method (Cardoso, Delgado and Barata, 2015) adopt the application of 3rd- degree polynomial equation to fix the dynamic component of the hand gestures

2.6.3 Rule-based Method

In this method, the input features are extracted and compared with the encoding rules that are attached to the recognized gestures (Su, 2000) and according to (*Depth camera based hand gesture recognition and its applications in Human-Computer-Interaction | IEEE Conference Publication | IEEE Xplore*, no date) rule-based method is that is suitable for the dynamic and static gesture which contain pre-encoded rule and features for input (Su, 2000)

This study mainly highlights the applications of Deep Learning and how thoughtful it can be in our daily lives. To, achieve such noble thinking of implementing Deep Learning in Sign Language, one should have a great knowledge of both Deep Learning and Sign Language.

CHAPTER 3

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Sign language recognition does not have a standard approach. Various approaches exist which are still seen as experimental approaches as reviewed in the previous chapter. The most common challenge every sign language recognition approach has is the availability of a well-populated and diverse dataset for sign language in general to train models from the scratch. Creating an efficient dataset requires a lot financially and the availability of a diverse population (every human differs in so many ways such as skin color, hand size, and many others) which is a whole project on its own.

My approach addresses this challenge to some extent with an innovative approach which I also view as an experimental approach because there is still room for improvement (Al-Qurishi, Khalid and Souissi, 2021).

3.1 Projected Method

I would be using Transfer learning with the Pose estimation approach, this would be done with open-source libraries. Transfer learning could simply be referred to as a Machine Learning method where a specific model developed for a task is also reused as the starting point for a model of the second task (Day and Khoshgoftaar, 2017), and Pose estimation could as well be referred to the use of a Machine Learning model to estimate the pose of a person from an image or a video by simply estimating the spatial locations of key body joints (*Pose estimation / TensorFlow Lite*, no date). As my starting point, I would be using an open-source pose estimation library MediaPipe.

3.2 Media Pipe

MediaPipe is a cross-platform pipeline framework to build custom machine learning solutions for live and streaming media (*MediaPipe: Google's Open Source Framework for ML solutions (2022 Guide) - viso.ai*, no date). MediaPipe has varieties of the solution, for my approach would use MediaPipe Hands.

MediaPipe Hands: MediaPipe Hand is a high-fidelity hand and finger tracking solution that provides precise real-world 21 3D hand Keypoints as shown (Figure 1)

Figure 1 key points

3.3 Requirements

This consist of the hardware and software require I used to perform my study

- Hardware Requirements: A standard computer with a working webcam
- Software requirement: This consists of the programming language, IDE (integrated development environment), and other libraries.
 - Programming language: Python programming language,
 - IDE: Jupiter notebook,
 - Libraries: Matplotlib: a library for data visualization, Sklearn: a library for evaluation matric and data splitting, OpenCV: a library for performing image processing and computer vision tasks and TensorFlow: a library for building a neural network.

3.4 Project Design

My proposed method is divided into 3 steps

1. Creating a sequence dataset in real-time.
2. Training a model with the sequence dataset
3. Make a real-time prediction

3.4.1 Creating a Sequence dataset in real-time

This step involved creating a dataset in real-time, using transfer learning and pose estimation. Converting sign language to sequential data was achieved by using the Mediapipe pose estimation library with other dependencies in real-time to extract my hand's 21 key points which are then written into a CSV file (this CSV file would be used to train the model). This process is achieved with functions written in a python programming language.

The Keypoints before being saved in a CSV file underwent some pre-processing steps. Each step was achieved with functions written in a python programming language (Appendix 5 and 6)

- **Keypoints coordinate:** The key point's coordinates by default are composed of the X, Y, and Z axis. X represents the width, Y represents the Height and Z represents the depth of the Input image.

```
[landmark {
  x: 0.745215117931366
  y: 0.8825769424438477
  z: 8.763799463906707e-09
}
landmark {
  x: 0.7006321549415588
  y: 0.8642742037773132
  z: -0.017469769343733788
}
landmark {
  x: 0.6652814149856567
  y: 0.8215782046318054
  z: -0.026524897664785385
}
}
```

Figure 2 coordinates

- **Convert to coordinates:** Converted the X and Y axis to coordinates by multiplying X with image width and Y with image height did not use Z-axis due to inaccuracy.

```
[[0, 0], [-24, 7], [-55, -1], [-72, -12], [-75, -24], [-59, -30], [-74, -38], [-81, -31], [-83, -22], [-53, -40], [-72, -48],
[-78, -39], [-78, -26], [-44, -50], [-66, -61], [-71, -49], [-70, -34], [-30, -60], [-49, -67], [-52, -53], [-49, -37]]
[[0, 0], [-25, 6], [-54, 0], [-70, -10], [-74, -22], [-63, -32], [-78, -39], [-83, -32], [-84, -23], [-56, -42], [-76, -50],
[-80, -39], [-79, -25], [-45, -52], [-67, -62], [-70, -47], [-67, -31], [-30, -61], [-50, -66], [-54, -52], [-51, -36]]
[[0, 0], [-25, 5], [-55, -3], [-74, -15], [-76, -30], [-61, -33], [-75, -40], [-81, -33], [-84, -26], [-54, -43], [-72, -50],
[-77, -40], [-78, -27], [-43, -52], [-64, -60], [-64, -43], [-58, -26], [-29, -62], [-50, -67], [-53, -52], [-49, -35]]
[[0, 0], [-25, 5], [-55, -3], [-74, -15], [-76, -30], [-61, -33], [-75, -40], [-81, -33], [-84, -26], [-54, -43], [-72, -50],
[-77, -40], [-78, -27], [-43, -52], [-64, -60], [-64, -43], [-58, -26], [-29, -62], [-50, -67], [-53, -52], [-49, -35]]
[[0, 0], [-27, 5], [-57, -4], [-75, -16], [-80, -30], [-63, -32], [-79, -39], [-81, -30], [-79, -20], [-56, -42], [-75, -49],
[-74, -34], [-68, -20], [-45, -52], [-67, -60], [-66, -42], [-58, -25], [-30, -61], [-51, -67], [-55, -51], [-50, -34]]
[[0, 0], [-27, 5], [-56, -4], [-73, -15], [-79, -27], [-62, -34], [-78, -42], [-83, -34], [-83, -24], [-55, -43], [-76, -52],
[-79, -39], [-77, -25], [-45, -53], [-67, -61], [-67, -44], [-60, -26], [-30, -62], [-51, -67], [-54, -52], [-50, -36]]
```

Figure 3 x,y coordinates

- **Convert to one dimension:** This is done to enable the sequence of each sign 21 key point to be written to a CSV file in rows

```

[[0, 0], [-24, 7], [-55, -1], [-72, -12], [-75, -24], [-59, -30], [-74, -38], [-81, -31], [-83, -22], [-53, -40], [-72, -48],
[-78, -39], [-78, -26], [-44, -50], [-66, -61], [-71, -49], [-70, -34], [-30, -60], [-49, -67], [-52, -53], [-49, -37]]
[[0, 0], [-25, 6], [-54, 0], [-70, -10], [-74, -22], [-63, -32], [-78, -39], [-83, -32], [-84, -23], [-56, -42], [-76, -50],
[-80, -39], [-79, -25], [-45, -52], [-67, -62], [-70, -47], [-67, -31], [-30, -61], [-50, -66], [-54, -52], [-51, -36]]
[[0, 0], [-25, 5], [-55, -3], [-74, -15], [-76, -30], [-61, -33], [-75, -40], [-81, -33], [-84, -26], [-54, -43], [-72, -50],
[-77, -40], [-78, -27], [-43, -52], [-64, -60], [-64, -43], [-58, -26], [-29, -62], [-50, -67], [-53, -52], [-49, -35]]
[[0, 0], [-25, 5], [-55, -3], [-74, -15], [-76, -30], [-61, -33], [-75, -40], [-81, -33], [-84, -26], [-54, -43], [-72, -50],
[-77, -40], [-78, -27], [-43, -52], [-64, -60], [-64, -43], [-58, -26], [-29, -62], [-50, -67], [-53, -52], [-49, -35]]
[[0, 0], [-27, 5], [-57, -4], [-75, -16], [-80, -30], [-63, -32], [-79, -39], [-81, -30], [-79, -20], [-56, -42], [-75, -49],
[-74, -34], [-68, -20], [-45, -52], [-67, -60], [-66, -42], [-58, -25], [-30, -61], [-51, -67], [-55, -51], [-50, -34]]
[[0, 0], [-27, 5], [-56, -4], [-73, -15], [-79, -27], [-62, -34], [-78, -42], [-83, -34], [-83, -24], [-55, -43], [-76, -52],
[-79, -39], [-77, -25], [-45, -53], [-67, -61], [-67, -44], [-60, -26], [-30, -62], [-51, -67], [-54, -52], [-50, -36]]

```

Figure 4 1 dimensional coordinates

- **Normalization:** This was done to minimize data redundancy

```

[0.0, 0.0, -0.3105590062111801, -0.031055900621118012, -0.5838509316770186, -0.21739130434782608, -0.7329192546583851, -0.416
1490683229814, -0.7701863354037267, -0.6086956521739131, -0.5217391304347826, -0.5838509316770186, -0.6335403726708074, -0.81
98757763975155, -0.6708074534161491, -0.782608695652174, -0.6521739130434783, -0.6645962732919255, -0.37267080745341613, -0.6
894409937888198, -0.484472049689441, -0.9565217391304348, -0.5031055900621118, -0.8633540372670807, -0.484472049689441, -0.70
80745341614907, -0.19875776397515527, -0.7515527950310559, -0.2981366459627329, -1.0, -0.3167701863354037, -0.869565217391304
3, -0.2919254658385093, -0.7080745341614907, -0.006211180124223602, -0.7763975155279503, -0.09937888198757763, -0.96894409937
8882, -0.13043478260869565, -0.8819875776397516, -0.11180124223602485, -0.7639751552795031]
[0.0, 0.0, -0.3105590062111801, -0.031055900621118012, -0.5838509316770186, -0.21739130434782608, -0.7329192546583851, -0.416
1490683229814, -0.7701863354037267, -0.6086956521739131, -0.5217391304347826, -0.5838509316770186, -0.6335403726708074, -0.81
98757763975155, -0.6708074534161491, -0.782608695652174, -0.6521739130434783, -0.6645962732919255, -0.37267080745341613, -0.6
894409937888198, -0.484472049689441, -0.9565217391304348, -0.5031055900621118, -0.8633540372670807, -0.484472049689441, -0.70
80745341614907, -0.19875776397515527, -0.7515527950310559, -0.2981366459627329, -1.0, -0.3167701863354037, -0.869565217391304
3, -0.2919254658385093, -0.7080745341614907, -0.006211180124223602, -0.7763975155279503, -0.09937888198757763, -0.96894409937
8882, -0.13043478260869565, -0.8819875776397516, -0.11180124223602485, -0.7639751552795031]

```

Figure 5 normalized coordinates

- **Saved to CSV as Sequence data:** The CSV file has forty three columns the first column the sequential identification of each sign and the other forty two columns are the X and Y axis of the 21 KeyPoints of my hand. Sequential identification 0 holds sign language “A” as shown (figure 6) and sequence identification 1 holds “B” as shown (figure 7)

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	W	
1																								
2	0	0	0	0.175439	-0.09211	0.285088	-0.27193	0.390351	-0.39474	0.486842	-0.45614	0.140351	-0.52632	0.127193	-0.70614	0.109649	-0.81579	0.087719	-0.91667	0.030702	-0.54386	0.017544	-0.75439	0.017544
3	0	0	0	0.011333	-0.26	-0.17333	-0.5	-0.41333	-0.60667	-0.58	-0.68667	-0.24667	-0.59333	-0.52	-0.78	-0.68667	-0.90667	-0.82667	-1	-0.36	-0.46	-0.67333	-0.49333	-0.49333
4	0	0	0	0.172566	-0.0885	0.283186	-0.26549	0.389381	-0.38938	0.482301	-0.45133	0.137168	-0.52212	0.123894	-0.70796	0.110619	-0.81858	0.088496	-0.92035	0.030973	-0.53982	0.013274	-0.75221	0.013274
5	0	0	0	0.034247	-0.25342	-0.15068	-0.49315	-0.39726	-0.60274	-0.55479	-0.67123	-0.23973	-0.60274	-0.5	-0.79452	-0.67808	-0.91096	-0.82192	-1	-0.34932	-0.47945	-0.66438	-0.5	-0.66438
6	0	0	0	0.176211	-0.08811	0.286344	-0.26432	0.387665	-0.38326	0.484851	-0.44493	0.145374	-0.52423	0.132159	-0.70485	0.114537	-0.81938	0.096916	-0.9163	0.035242	-0.54185	0.022026	-0.7533	0.022026
7	0	0	0	0.034247	-0.26027	-0.15068	-0.5	-0.38356	-0.60274	-0.54795	-0.68493	-0.23288	-0.60959	-0.49315	-0.78767	-0.66438	-0.91096	-0.80137	-1	-0.34247	-0.47945	-0.65068	-0.5	-0.65068
8	0	0	0	0.175439	-0.09211	0.280702	-0.26754	0.385965	-0.39035	0.47807	-0.45175	0.135965	-0.52193	0.127193	-0.70175	0.114035	-0.81579	0.096491	-0.91228	0.026316	-0.53947	0.017544	-0.74561	0.017544
9	0	0	0	0.034247	-0.25342	-0.15068	-0.49315	-0.39726	-0.60274	-0.55479	-0.67123	-0.23973	-0.60274	-0.5	-0.79452	-0.67808	-0.91096	-0.82192	-1	-0.34932	-0.47945	-0.66438	-0.5	-0.66438

Figure 6 letter A sequence

86	1	0	0	0.260417	-0.09375	0.46875	-0.36458	0.635417	-0.54167	0.833333	-0.59375	0.291667	-0.76042	0.489583	-0.94792	0.697917	-0.88542	0.833333	-0.77083	0.208333	-0.80208	0.479167	-1	0.
87	1	0	0	-0.25882	-0.08235	-0.44706	-0.31765	-0.58824	-0.49412	-0.74118	-0.61176	-0.41176	-0.48235	-0.62353	-0.62353	-0.82353	-0.68235	-0.98824	-0.68235	-0.36471	-0.55294	-0.58824	-0.71765	-0.
88	1	0	0	0.257732	-0.08247	0.463918	-0.35052	0.639175	-0.51546	0.835052	-0.58763	0.309278	-0.76289	0.494845	-0.96907	0.701031	-0.89691	0.835052	-0.78351	0.226804	-0.79381	0.494845	-1	0.
89	1	0	0	0.278351	-0.09278	0.484536	-0.36082	0.649485	-0.51546	0.845361	-0.58763	0.329897	-0.76289	0.525773	-0.94845	0.731959	-0.8866	0.865979	-0.7732	0.247423	-0.79381	0.515464	-1	0.
90	1	0	0	-0.23256	-0.0814	-0.43023	-0.33721	-0.60465	-0.51163	-0.80233	-0.59302	-0.36047	-0.56977	-0.5814	-0.72093	-0.80233	-0.73256	-0.97674	-0.68605	-0.31395	-0.63953	-0.55814	-0.7907	-0.
91	1	0	0	0.247423	-0.08247	0.474227	-0.35052	0.639175	-0.51546	0.835052	-0.58763	0.319588	-0.74227	0.505155	-0.92784	0.71134	-0.87629	0.845361	-0.76289	0.237113	-0.7732	0.484536	-1	0.
92	1	0	0	-0.25	-0.09524	-0.44048	-0.35714	-0.61905	-0.5119	-0.80952	-0.58333	-0.32143	-0.64286	-0.55952	-0.78571	-0.80952	-0.77381	-0.9881	-0.70238	-0.2619	-0.70238	-0.54762	-0.88095	-0.
93	1	0	0	0.260417	-0.08333	0.46875	-0.36458	0.645833	-0.52083	0.833333	-0.59375	0.302083	-0.77083	0.510417	-0.94792	0.71875	-0.875	0.854167	-0.76042	0.21875	-0.80208	0.5	-1	0.
94	1	0	0	-0.24359	-0.10256	-0.44872	-0.37179	-0.62821	-0.55128	-0.83333	-0.64103	-0.38462	-0.64103	-0.58974	-0.82051	-0.82051	-0.83333	-1	-0.78205	-0.32051	-0.69231	-0.55128	-0.91026	-0.
95	1	0	0	0.268041	-0.09278	0.484536	-0.36082	0.649485	-0.52577	0.845361	-0.58763	0.319588	-0.75258	0.515464	-0.93814	0.71134	-0.87629	0.845361	-0.7732	0.237113	-0.79381	0.505155	-1	0.
96	1	0	0	-0.23457	-0.07407	-0.44444	-0.35802	-0.62963	-0.54321	-0.82716	-0.62963	-0.33333	-0.67901	-0.5679	-0.83951	-0.81481	-0.82716	-1	-0.74074	-0.2716	-0.7284	-0.53086	-0.93827	-0.
97	1	0	0	0.270833	-0.08333	0.479167	-0.35417	0.65625	-0.51042	0.854167	-0.57292	0.322917	-0.76042	0.520833	-0.95833	0.71875	-0.88542	0.854167	-0.77083	0.239583	-0.79167	0.520833	-1	0.
98	1	0	0	-0.23596	-0.04494	-0.4382	-0.30337	-0.61798	-0.47191	-0.80899	-0.55056	-0.31461	-0.57303	-0.5618	-0.70787	-0.79775	-0.70787	-0.98876	-0.61798	-0.25843	-0.65169	-0.53933	-0.79775	-0.
99	1	0	0	0.260417	-0.0625	0.46875	-0.33333	0.635417	-0.5	0.833333	-0.58333	0.302083	-0.75	0.489583	-0.92708	0.6875	-0.88542	0.822917	-0.80208	0.21875	-0.79167	0.479167	-1	0.

Figure 7 letter B sequence

3.4.2 Training a model with the sequence dataset

The CSV file which is now my dataset is used for training a Neural network model. Building and training a model involves various steps which are as follows.

- **Import and install libraries (Appendix 14):** The required libraries are installed and imported, these libraries would enable the building of the model, splitting of the dataset, and training.
- **Set destination path (Appendix 15):** The destination path for the CSV dataset is stated and the path where the model weights would be saved is stated.
- **Set output class (Appendix 16):** The number of signs the model would predict is stated.
- **Dataset Reading and Splitting (Appendix 17):** The dataset is imported and split into 70% for training and 30% of the dataset for validation.
- **Model Building (Appendix 18):** Using transfer learning with pose estimation reduces the complexity of the model building. A sequential model was built, which is a machine learning model that's inputs and output sequence of data. (*Sequence Models & Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) | by Santhoopa Jayawardhana | Towards Data Science, no date*). The model is made up of an Input layer, a Dense layer, a Dropout layer, an output layer, and an activation function.
 - a. **Input layer:** This is the beginning of the workflow of a neural network model
 - b. **Dense layer:** This is deeply connected with the preceding layer.
 - c. **Dropout layer:** This helps prevent overfitting. Overfitting happens when a model fits exactly against its training data.
 - d. **Output layer:** This is the last layer in a neural network model, this is where the desired prediction is obtained.
 - e. **Activation functions:** These are functions that define the output and input of a given node or layer.

```

Model: "sequential"

```

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
dropout (Dropout)	(None, 42)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 20)	860
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 20)	0
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 10)	210
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 10)	110

```

Total params: 1,180
Trainable params: 1,180
Non-trainable params: 0

```

Figure 8 Neural Networks Summary

- **Model callbacks(Appendix 19):** This executes a specified action at different points of training a neural network model.

- **The model compilation (Appendix 20):** This is the last stage in the model-building process before training starts. It checks for format errors and defines the loss function, learning rate, and metric.
- **Training Model (Appendix 21):** This is the stage where training starts. The dataset is fed into the model with my desired parameters.

Figure 9 training architecture

3.4.3 Make a real-time prediction

Making real time prediction involves converting the trained weights using TensorFlow lite (*TensorFlow Lite*, no date)(Appendix 24) This enables models to be tested in real time. These converted weights would be used to build a Model classification Class (Appendix 12).

- **Application Flow Chat (Appendix 13)**

This shows the steps and process the application went through to perform sign language recognition as shown in (figure 10).

Figure 10 code algorithm

CHAPTER 4

4.0 Results

The chapter gives insight into and a summary of the outcome of my approach. To test my approach the British sign language was used, letter A to E and number 1- 5 in a total of 10 signs,500 sequences of each was extracted in real-time with a total of 5000. The Sequence was saved in CSV which was used to train a neural network.

4.1 Training setup and result

The CVS file which is now a dataset is split into training and validation, 70% for training and 30 % for validation. During training, two call-back functions were used “early stopping” which was used to avoid overfitting by stopping training once there is no improvement, and “model checkpoint” which saves the weight after each epoch.

```
Epoch 00232: saving model to keypoints\keypointClassifier.hdf5
Epoch 233/1000
24/24 [=====] - 0s 10ms/step - loss: 0.7120 - accuracy: 0.7380
- val_loss: 0.2710 - val_accuracy: 0.9420

Epoch 00233: saving model to keypoints\keypointClassifier.hdf5
Epoch 00233: early stopping
```

Figure 11 training log

Model evaluation (Appendix 22): the accuracy of the model is evaluated and an accuracy of 94% was achieved at epoch 233

Figure 12 accuracy frequency

Figure 13 loss frequency

4.2 Confusion Matrix

This is the summary of the performance of the predicted classes

Figure 14 confusion matrix

Classification Report

Classification Report				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.94	1.00	0.97	164
1	1.00	0.98	0.99	152
2	1.00	1.00	1.00	155
3	0.96	0.88	0.92	154
4	0.93	0.94	0.93	143
5	0.82	0.91	0.86	141
6	0.99	0.97	0.98	143
7	0.89	0.99	0.94	158
8	1.00	0.71	0.83	132
9	0.94	1.00	0.97	158
accuracy			0.94	1500
macro <u>avg</u>	0.95	0.94	0.94	1500
weighted <u>avg</u>	0.95	0.94	0.94	1500

Figure 15 classification report

Performance in real time

British sign language was used as a case study with letters A -E and number 1 -5.

Figure 16 British Sign Language A

Figure 17 British Sign Language B

Figure 18 British Sign Language C

Figure 19 British Sign Language D

Figure 20 British Sign Language E

Figure 21 British Sign Language 1

#

Figure 22 British Sign Language 2

Figure 23 British Sign Language 3

Figure 24 British Sign Language 4

Figure 25 British Sign Language 5

Challenges.

CHAPTER 5

5.0 Conclusion

There are a lot of problems in interpreting sign language for normal people. One of the prime problems is the lack of training in sign language. The majority of people around the world have zero knowledge of sign language. In this field, the application of Computer Vision with Deep Learning has easily helped the disabled to interact with normal people normally.

Sign-learning annotation is one of the effective approaches based on computer vision and machine learning concepts and can be used for improving collaboration with the deaf community. The fingerspelling recognition technique can be used for educating deaf people and one with difficulties in sign languages using various finger notation and almost 71% of recognition is almost achieved using skeletal wireframe image training data sets of fingerspelling and the MediaPipe estimation model is also effective for this approach. Now, there are various hand gesture techniques utilized for interacting with deaf people, and some of them are discussed in this report.

In the course of the study and the findings, tangible contributions have been added to eliminate the interference of human interpreters as regards British Sign Language by relying on the developed application with the help of pose estimation library (Mediaipe) for easy creation of real-time dataset to enhance communication with those that have impairment of speech. However, the research work has also projected avenues for future research work

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Appendix

Appendix 1(Libraries installation)

```
!pip install mediapipe sklearn tensorflow matplotlib opencv
```

Appendix 2 (Import libraries)

```
import tensorflow as tf, cv2 as cv, numpy as np, mediapipe as mp
```

Appendix 3 (Status selection)

```
def select_status(Option,Update):  
    Key = -1  
    if 48 <= Option <= 72:  
        key = Option - 48  
    if Selection == 101:  
        Update = 0  
    if Option == 122:  
        Option = 1  
    return Key, Option
```

Appendix 4 (Bounding rectangle)

```
def bounding_rectangle(image, keypoints):  
    ImageWidth = image.shape[1]  
    ImageHeight = image.shape[0]  
    ResultArray = np.empty((0, 2), int)  
  
    for _, keypoint in enumerate(keypoints.keypoint):  
  
        Keypoint_X = min(int(keypoint.x * ImageWidth), ImageWidth - 1)  
        Keypoint_Y = min(int(keypoint.y * ImageHeight), ImageHeight - 1)  
  
        KeyPoints = [np.array((Keypoint_X, Keypoint_Y))]  
  
        ResultArray = np.append(ResultArray, KeyPoints, )  
  
    a, b, c, d = cv.boundingRect(ResultArray)  
  
    return [a, b, a + c, b + d]
```

Appendix 5 (Calculate Keypoints)

```
def calculate_keypoints(image, keypoints):  
    ImageWidth = image.shape[1]  
    ImageHeight = image.shape[0]  
  
    KeyPoints = []  
    for _, Keypoint in enumerate(keypoints.keypoint):  
        Keypoint_X = min(int(Keypoint.x * ImageWidth), ImageWidth - 1)  
        Keypoint_Y = min(int(Keypoint.y * ImageHeight), ImageHeight - 1)
```

```
KeyPoints.append([Keypoint_X, Keypoint_Y])
```

```
return KeyPoints
```

Appendix 6 (Keypoints Pre processing)

```
def keypoints_pre_processing(keypointlist):  
    copykeypointlist = copy.deepcopy(keypointlist)  
    A, B = 0, 0  
    for x, Keypoint in enumerate(copykeypointlist):  
        if x == 0:  
            A,B = Keypoint[0], Keypoint[1]  
  
            copykeypointlist[x][0] = copykeypointlist[x][0] - A  
            copykeypointlist[x][1] = copykeypointlist[x][1] - B  
  
    copykeypointlist = list(itertools.chain.from_iterable(copykeypointlist))  
  
    norm = max (list(map(abs, copykeypointlist)))  
    def absolute(z):  
        return z / norm  
  
    copykeypointlist = list(map(absolute copykeypointlist))  
  
    return copykeypointlist
```

Appendix 7 (key points saved CSV)

```

def keypoints_to_csv(Key, update, keypointlist):
    if update == 0:
        pass
    if update == 3 and (4 <= Key <= 38):
        Path = 'keypoints/keypoints.csv'
        with open(Path, 'a', newline='') as k:
            save = csv.save (k)
            save.([Key, *keypointlist])
    return

```

Appendix 8 (Drawing Keypoints)

```

def draw_keypoint(img, keypointlist):
    cv.line(img, tuple(keypointlist[2]), tuple(keypointlist[3]),
            (255, 255, 255), 2)
    cv.line(img, tuple(keypointlist[3]), tuple(keypointlist[4]),
            (0, 0, 0), 6)
    cv.line(img, tuple(keypointlist[3]), tuple(keypointlist[4]),
            (255, 255, 255), 2)

```

Appendix 9 (Drawing bounding rectangle)

```

def d_b_r(image, den):
    cv.rectangle(image, (den[5], den[7]), (den[4], den[8]),(3, 2, 2), 6)
    return image

```

Appendix 10 (Display Signs)

```

def Display (image,den, detetion, reg):
    cv.rectangle(image, (den[5], den[7]), (den[4], den[1] - 18),(3,2, 1), -9)

```

```

dis= dection.selection[0].label[0:]
if reg = 7:
    dis = dis - '/' - dis

return image

```

Appendix 11(Notification)

```

def d_e_i(image, update, key):

    updatedis = ['Logging_key']
    if 4 <= update <= 9:
        return image

```

Appendix 12 (Keypoint interpreter)

```

Def Classifier(interpret,x,y):

    input_index = interpreter.get_input_details()[0]["index"]
    output_index = interpreter.get_output_details()[0]["index"]

    interpreter = Interpreter(path=Path,num_threads=1)

    interpreter.allocate_tensors()
    input_index = interpreter.get_input()
    output_details = interpreter.get_output()

    input_details_tensor_index = input_details[0]['index']

```

```
interpreter.set_tensor(input_dex, np.array([keypointList])
interpreter.invoke()

output_details_tensor_index = self.output_details[0]['index']

output = interpreter.tensor(output_index)
predicted_label = np.argmax(output)

return predicted_label
```

Appendix 13 (application function)

```
def Application():

    mediapipehand = me.solutions.hands
    mediapipehands =
mediapipeHand.Hands(static_image_mode=True,max_num_hands=2,min_detection_confidence
= 0.5, min_tracking_confidence= 0.5,)

    Classifier = Classifier()

    with open(r"C:\pathkeypointLabel.csv") as k:

        KeypointLabels = csv.reader(k)
        KeypointLabels = [column [0] for column in KeypointLabels]

    Option = 4
```

```
while True:

    option = cv.waitKey(12)
    if option == 15:
        break
    key, update = option_update(option, update)

    updated, image = cap.read()
    if not updated:
        break
    image = cv.flip(image, 2)

    BGRImage = copy.deepcopy(image)

    img = cv.cvtColor(img, cv.COLOR_BGR2RGB)

    image.flags.writeable = False
    results = hands.process(image)
    img.flags.writeable = True

    if results.multi_hand_landmarks is not None:
        for multiHandKeypoints, multiHandedness in
zip(results.multi_hand_landmarks, results.multi_handedness):

            den = br(BGRImage, multiHandKeypoints)
            KeyPointList = calculate_keypoints(BGRImage, multiHandKeypoints)
```

```
keypointsPreProcessed = keypoints_pre_processing(  
    KeyPointList)
```

```
keypoints_to_csv(key, status, keypointsPreProcessed)
```

```
SignId = Classifier(keypointsPreProcessed)
```

```
cap.release()
```

```
cv.destroyAllWindows()
```

Appendix 14(import libraries)

```
import tensorflow as tf , numpy as np  
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
```

Appendix 15(set path)

```
csvdataset = 'keypoints/keypoint.csv'  
modelpath = 'keypoints/keypointClassifier.hdf5'  
tflite_save_path = 'keypoints/keypointClassifier.tflite'
```

Appendix 16 (predicted classes)

```
CLASSES = 10
```

Appendix 17()

```
X = np.loadtxt(csvdataset, usecols=list(range(1, (21 * 2) + 1)))
y = np.loadtxt(csvdataset, usecols=(0))
X_train, X_validation, y_train, y_validation = train_test_split(X, y, train_size=0.70)
```

Appendix 18

```
model = tf.keras.models.Sequential([
    tf.keras.layers.Input((21 * 2, )),
    tf.keras.layers.Dense(30, activation='relu'),
    tf.keras.layers.Dense(20, activation='relu'),
    tf.keras.layers.Dropout(0.4)
    tf.keras.layers.Dense(CLASSES, activation='softmax')
```

Appendix 19(callback)

```
Savingcallback = tf.keras.callbacks.ModelCheckpoint(
    modelpath, verbose=5,)
stopcallback = tf.keras.callbacks.EarlyStopping(patience=30, verbose=5)
```

Appendix 20()

```
model.compile ( optimizer='adam',loss='sparse_categorical_crossentropy',
metrics=['accuracy']
)
```

Appendix 21()

```
model.fit(X_train,y_train,epochs=500,batch_size=150,validation_data=(X_validation,
y_validation),callbacks=[savecallback, stopcallback])
```

Appendix 22

```
evaluation_loss, evaluation_accuracy = model.evaluate(X_validation, y_validation,  
batch_size=150)
```

Appendix 23

```
model = tf.keras.models.load_model(modelpath)
```

```
convert = tf.lite.TFLiteConverter.from_keras_model(model)  
convert.optimizations = [tf.lite.Optimize.DEFAULT]  
tfmodel = convert.convert()
```

Appendix 24 (Convert model to tensorflowlit)